

The impact of the knowledge-oriented leadership and culture on innovation and performance of organizational with emphasis on the role of mediator of Practices and process of knowledge management

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Abstract

Due to the current growing market conditions, companies and organizations should be able to identify all of their internal capabilities to provide a more productive performance. These strategic inclinations require the proper application of factors affecting the organization's performance. One of the most important issues in this area is determining the mediating role of variables that facilitate the impact of culture and knowledge-oriented leadership on organizational performance. Accordingly, this study aimed to determine the impact of leadership and knowledge-oriented culture on organizational innovation and performance with an emphasis on the role of methods intermediary and the process of knowledge creation. The statistical population of this study consisted of 600 production units from Eshtehard industrial town. Using the Cochran formula, 236 managers of companies were selected as statistical sample. In order to collect data, standard questionnaires (with verified justifiability and stability) were used based on a 5-degree Likert scale. Data analysis was performed using structural equation modeling (PLS software). The results showed that knowledge-oriented culture and leadership through the intermediary variables (knowledge creation process and knowledge management (KM) practices could predict the performance of innovation by 71.1% ($R^2=0.711$). Leadership of knowledge creation and innovation performance can predict 86.3% of organizational performance changes ($R^2=0.863$).

Keywords: Knowledge-oriented Leadership, Knowledge-oriented Culture, Innovation Performance, Organizational Performance, Knowledge management practices, Knowledge creation process.

Introduction

Evidence from a large number of studies suggests that the performance of knowledge management-based systems is a function of how it is used by senior managers and leaders in organizations (Andreeva & Ikhilchik, 2011; Bratianu & Orzea, 2010; Gavrilova & Andreeva, 2012; Nold, 2012; Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995; Rusly, Corner, & Sun, 2011) it can be stated that the usefulness of using knowledge management is a function of how to lead a set to implement it (Donate & de Pablo, 2015; Mohsen Abadi & Azadeh Del, 2016).

Accordingly, although the importance of knowledge management and its use for different organizations is no doubt, reports that recently have been published, including the Report of Bain's Management Techniques and Tools (2011), indicate a low level of satisfaction with the use of KM and its results and application. This issue has led some studies to explore the intermediary variables and factors affecting the improvement of KM performance (Ayub et al, 2016; Donate & de Pablo, 2015). Understanding these factors to resolve this issue is one of the vague and unknown aspects of present research. On the other hand, one of the most important challenges in this field is designing and implementing methods for the proper implementation of knowledge management for managers, which is difficult, and the efficiency and success of these methods largely depends on their optimal compatibility with organizational factors (Bierly & Daly, 2002). As a result, managers need to provide the desirable conditions in order to be able to ensure, by using the right methods, the

improvement of performance and organizational innovation (Chen & Huang, 2009; Donate & de Pablo, 2015; Lin, 2011). However, there has been a research gap with limited studies in this field, and we still do not have an adequate understanding of how to apply KM and desired practices in this area. Examining in this field, only two studies (Ayub et al, 2016; Donate & de Pablo, 2015) can be mentioned, each of which refers to specific variables in this area.

In a study by Ayub et al (2016), evidence suggest that in order to the improvement of the efficiency of KM in organizations, should be considered the mediator variable called the knowledge creation process. Donate and de Pablo (2015) also refer to another variable called KM practices.

The process of knowledge creation involves: socialization (acquisition of knowledge from others, such as work groups, holding meetings), externalization (capturing experts knowledge and gaining their experiences); combination (creating databases and integrating information and creating access to it on web pages for combining Knowledge in all departments), internalization (attention to learning and training of human resources (Ayub et al, 2011) and knowledge management practices also refers to the extraction methods of current knowledge through the transfer, sharing and use of these resources (Donate & de Pablo, 2015).

However, in both studies, it has been shown that the practical application of the knowledge creation process and KM practices will not be practically effective without management and leadership support. In other words, the use of knowledge-oriented culture (Ayub et al., 2016) and knowledge-oriented leadership (Donate & de Pablo 2015) should be considered the prerequisites for the effectiveness of KM in the organization. But so far, a direct and independent study has failed to integrate the presented models. Accordingly, in the present study, the combination of the two models is to be considered through structural equation modeling.

Using structural equation modeling, one can simultaneously estimate cause-and-effect relationships among many independent and dependent variables (Seo et al et al., 2015) and determine through which path the most desirable efficiency of KM can be realized: through Knowledge-oriented Knowledge- Knowledge creation process (Ayub et al. 2016) or knowledge-oriented leadership- KM practices (Donate & de Pablo, 2015). The purpose of using KM practices is to create better innovation performance (Zack et al., 2009; Darroch and McNaughton, 2002) and more desirable organizational performance (Pandey & Dutta, 2013; Nonaka & Toyama, 2003). Based on this, we tried to answer the following basic questions in the present study: How do KM practices and knowledge creation process play a role in the relationship between knowledge-oriented culture and leadership with organizational performance and innovation? In the following, the article focuses on providing a theoretical framework and developing hypotheses, in which the conceptual model is drawn up at the end. Subsequently, the research method and the findings are presented. At the end of the article, in the conclusion section, the explanation and comparison of the findings of the present study with other studies has been undertaken.

1. Theoretical framework and the development of assumptions

1.1 The relationship between knowledge-oriented culture and KM

The component of culture as the most influential and social factor and technology are considered as the most important factors in the sharing of knowledge. Before any activity in the process of KM, it has to be invested in the subject of culture. In fact, culture is the supporter of KM and reduces costs in knowledge production and improves organizational performance, creating a collaborative culture among employees creates group activities in their work (Ayub et al., 2016). Cultural factors can be considered as failure factors of KM, which can be turned into success by solving problems. Knowledge-oriented culture is a culture that values knowledge and encourages its creation, sharing and utilization (Akhavan & Imani, 2015).

The development of knowledge-oriented culture, along with the encouragement of behaviors such as the creation and sharing of knowledge, is one of the objectives of KM initiatives in the organization. Culture has a deep link with knowledge in organizations. In fact, any discussion of knowledge in the organization's environment without a specific reference to its cultural status is like moving in the wrong (Ayub et al., 2016). The need to pay attention to organizational culture is such that experts believed that if there is to be an effective and sustainable changes in an organization, the culture of that organization must undergo a change. In other words, the success and failure of organizations should be sought in its culture. Therefore, managers, relying on culture and exploiting it, can free themselves from traditional solutions and provide new solutions for the growth of the organization and its development. In any case, today, culture is an important element of the managed equation and its role and effect on organizational performance are well defined for management researchers. Hence, wise managers are helpness to pay attention to culture (Asaghar, 2013). The influence of cultural factors on the effectiveness of KM programs is undeniable. Each organization's culture, due to the inclusion of a value system, affects the behavior of individuals, may be in many cultures, given that "knowledge is power". This attitude leads to the hoarding of knowledge; therefore, this culture should be promoted to allow people to share their knowledge with others.

1.2 The relationship between knowledge-oriented culture and the process of knowledge creation

Knowledge, especially the implicit knowledge, is disseminated if its proper culture is created. In order to create an appropriate culture for transfer and exchange of knowledge, managers must move away from fear-oriented approaches so that individuals can easily express their knowledge easily even if such knowledge sharing does not produce significant and meaningful results. The realization of this approach requires the abandonment of obedience-based controls and moving toward control approaches is based on commitment. The role of managers in creating an appropriate culture for the dissemination of knowledge is important, they must create environments in which the members understand each other. In such environments where knowledge culture exists, learning takes place (Schein, 2011).

Regarding the impact and importance of culture in knowledge creation and its dissemination, it can be said that it leads to the creation of synergistic harmonic environments. If in an organization, values and culture encourage useful learning and knowledge creation, all functions of the organization will change, so the biggest challenge is not to change culture from "knowledge is power" but to "share knowledge is power" ; A subject that has been emphasized in Islam in centuries ago in the Hadith of Sharif: Zakat of science is to publish it (Vazifeh Doost et al., 2012). The importance of the knowledge-oriented culture in the organization for the success of knowledge creation is due to the fact that any organizational change will be successful when the whole organization and all its members are committed to this process of change, and all will try to succeed. Effective implementation of practices of the process of knowledge creation requires acceptance and universal support, and there must be certain behaviors and attitudes among the members of the organization (Lange, P. and Coltham, 2009). The behavior of individuals in an organization is determined more by the culture that is formed in the organization not by the orders of senior managers. Therefore, the implementation of many organizational strategies such as knowledge creation will face difficulties in the event of incompatibility with the organization's culture (Suppiah, and Singh, 2010). Creating and sharing knowledge are intangible activities that could not be created by force. Only when knowledge-oriented culture is felt and created by the members of the organization, knowledge creation can lead to excellent merit. Hence, cooperation, coordination and empowered teams of employees should be considered as standard attitudes in the KM environment and supported. Proper knowledge-oriented culture can have a positive tendency to share knowledge and innovation (Davenport, and Prusak, 2000).

1.3 The relationship between the process of knowledge creation and organizational performance

Given the role of new knowledge in the survival and growth of an organization, sometimes created knowledge has more importance than existing knowledge. New knowledge allows the organization to improve its performance, develop its capability and use more appropriately from existing resources. Consequently, the realization of concepts such as continuous improvement, organizational development and the acquisition of sustainable competitive advantage depends on the continuity of the knowledge creation process in the organization (Arvin et al., 2014).

Knowledge as an important source of competitive advantage and value creation, as an essential element for sustainable development and in general, is recognized as a determinant factor for companies with global goals. Additionally, the knowledge that companies recognize is a dynamic resource that requires nutrition and accurate management. The process of knowledge creation increases responsiveness, efficiency, flexibility in the organization, which results in competitive advantage for the organization, organizational innovation and organizational performance (Tomas & Hult, 2003). In the current era, organizations will succeed that to devote greater share of knowledge creation to them, and with its proper management can effectively and efficiently implement organizational and individual goals. On the other hand, human resources are creative and user of knowledge and their performance plays an important role in the performance and success of the organization (Liao et al., 2011).

1.4 The relationship of knowledge-oriented leadership and the process of knowledge creation

Knowledge-oriented leadership is a model that has the potential of organizational transformation and conversion, as well as the ability to develop positive-thinking organizations whose people are in peace, and the organization's performance can not only be associated with this, but it can also reach its maximum level (Ayub et al., 2016). One of these functions is knowledge creation that brings competitive advantage to organizations. In fact, the factors that can accelerate or threaten the creation of knowledge in the organization is the role of leadership in the organization (Sobhi, 2011).

Achieving knowledge creation is one of the necessities of any organization. Knowledge creation with the appropriate leadership style has a two-sided relationship. Knowledge-oriented leadership encourages individuals to knowledge creation and always tries to induce the importance of knowledge creation within an organization (Tomas & Hult, 2003).

1.5 The relationship between knowledge-oriented leadership and innovation performance

Knowledge-oriented leadership behavior and innovation performance with respect to KM practices can be explained by the fact that knowledge-oriented leadership is essential for technology-focused organizations to improve the performance of innovation through effective development and implementation of knowledge management practices (Ayub et al. 2016). Knowledge-oriented leadership acts as a driving force for KM practices that indirectly relates to innovation performance. In fact, the more the corporate knowledge-oriented leadership level is, the more KM practices developed, which in turn affects the performance of innovation (Donate & De Pablo, 2015). Companies can use knowledge-oriented behavior to expand KM practices and enhance the willingness of employees to innovate. Managers need to create the ideal environment to make possible the company's use of KM practices and designs through designing tools such as human resources management practices (Lin, 2011).

Knowledge-oriented leadership is essential for modern organizations. This approach is rapidly evolving and progressing, and there is a lot of attention to increasing efficiency and improving the effectiveness of organizational processes, along with continuous innovation. The need for knowledge leadership stems from the fact that knowledge practices are considered an important element in the performance of innovation and access to sustainable competitive advantage (Safari, Azadeh Del, 2015).

1.6 The relationship between knowledge leadership and KM

Knowledge leaders need to recognize and reward such efforts instead of encouraging negative behaviors that put the transfer, sharing and exploitation of knowledge at risk. In order to benefit from the processes of discovery and knowledge extraction, organizational leadership in knowledge-oriented organizations means leadership through knowledge. In other words, the leaders of the organization must lead the knowledge workers to learn and apply knowledge and thereby achieve the goals of the organization's knowledge. Knowledge-oriented leadership implies ownership of the prominent role of KM in an organization that leads to understanding and identifying opportunities for innovation (Teece, 2009).

Leaders should integrate divergent behaviors, depending on the circumstances, in order to strengthen and promote innovation in the organization. Very creative and innovative organizations, combining exploration and knowledge extraction activities to achieve dual power, must be able to direct the organization's members to achieve goals in different circumstances, based on distinct requirements (Rosing, 2011).

According to this issue, researchers express their doubts about the merits and advantages of traditional, heroic and transformative leadership in learning, and instead, they support of another kind of leadership-learning leadership, whereby Knowledge organizations are created by combining transformational leadership patterns (focusing on exchanges of followers in the form of profits, rewards, incentives and personal benefits) and interactive leadership patterns (focusing on motivation and inspiring others to utilize their maximum power)(Williams, Sullivan, 2011).

Generally, the combination pattern of knowledge leadership must lead the KM techniques to create, transfer, store, and apply knowledge in the organization. In addition, knowledge-oriented leadership should include transparent communication, taking into account the expectations of knowledge workers and the goals of the organization, as well as motivational elements (Schermerhorn, 2012).

Motivation is another factor for knowledge- oriented leadership. Two implicit motivations (role modeling) and explicit motivation (reward) have a positive relationship with the success and development of KM (von Krogh, 2012). One of the most important tasks of managers is to recognize various motivational factors affect people differently. Therefore, leaders should use a range of approaches depending on the preferences of the members of the organization. Therefore, leaders should use a range of approaches depending on the preferences of the members of the organization (Mugheli, Sepand Asa, 2015). Knowledge-oriented leadership in KM development combines the aspects of both transformational and interactive leadership, and also includes elements of motivation and communication. In addition, the motivational elements and special rewards for these activities help the organization to create appropriate conditions and develop activities to disseminate and share knowledge and transform (rendition) knowledge that leads to new ideas (Miller, 2007).

1.7 Relationship between KM and organizational performance

Given the importance of organizations in the 21st century, the need to pay attention to KM has become undeniable. Informative orientation of organizations to KM will provide their relief contexts from traditional bureaucratic structures and turning to new management systems in the world. In addition to the importance of KM, what is emphasized by managers and organizations is organizational performance. Today, study the factors affecting the performance of organizations are very important and most managers find that improving organizational performance is very effective in achieving the goals. In today's over-competitive world, achieving maximum productivity is not an ideal, but an necessity, and organizations, regardless of their size, have to improve human and organizational performance to achieve this essential goal (Zarrin, 2011).

Global competition and the challenges facing trade and industry have put pressure on organizations to create sustainable competitive advantage. Knowledge is considered as the basis and the main factor of competition. Alongside knowledge, innovation is also considered as the main driving force for the prosperity and success of organizations and the economy as a whole. On the other hand, for organizations, the customer is the focus of profitability and growth and should be at the focus of attention. Since KM is considered as one of the infrastructure factors in creating technical and managerial systems, the use of KM along with customer relationship management provides organizations with the opportunity to more likely identify market opportunities and by creating innovation, achieve to improved performance and increased competitive advantage (Alegre, et al. 2013).

KM guarantees long-term benefits to organizations and communities and their utilization of human, intellectual and informational capital. Management thinkers believe in the benefits of employing KM, but increasing organizational learning includes advanced management of intellectual assets, increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of operations, and continuous progress of the organization (Schmitz et al., 2014). The use of KM practices that often rely on information and communication technologies will lead to positive organizational outcomes such as upgrading communications, higher levels of employees participation, efficiency in problem solving, better performance at the time of presentation to market, more desirable financial performance, better marketing practices, upgrading the project team's performance, and thus broader approval of the role of KM in overall organizational success (Lee et al. 2012).

1.8 The relationship between KM and innovation

Nowadays, innovation in the present technological space is necessary for organizations, and most organizations are looking for new ideas. In this regard, the organization's experts are trying to use their knowledge to deliver products or services that customers need and create a foundation that innovation as learning is a continuous process because the purpose of KM and the secret of these modern organizations lies in innovation. KM experts believe that the mechanisms of innovation and KM processes can be adapted (Dehghan Najm, 2009).

Knowledge is the most important asset of any organization, and an organization that benefits from it will deal better with the existing challenges and will be more successful in the area of competition (Howells, 2008). The present age is the era of tremendous changes in technology. An era in which its intellectual structure is fraught with deepening of information and paying attention to the contribution of creative and knowledge-oriented human resources instead of functional human performance. Hence, awareness management wants to use more and more knowledge tools to confront and deal with factors of uncertainty, maintain position and create creativity and innovation to expand its competitive field (Stover, 2004). This requires that the organization, by valuation KM, places it in the class of its priority programs as a strategic and necessary need to advance in the field of competitiveness. In today's world, societies and organizations are seeking sustainable competitive advantage (Baladehi, Arabi 2014).

In this regard, KM is a useful tool for organizations to develop their capital, encourage innovation and maximize their desirable performance (Talebi, 2007). KM is a new driver that can reduce gaps and distances. KM as a management key tool of the new century in organizations as the provider of the field of readout, creation, training, sharing and exchange, upgrade organizing, maintenance and dissemination of knowledge at the organization level, especially at sections level, will lead to the formation of training methods new approaches, effective use of existing knowledge, readiness to receive and use information and modern knowledge to develop it and technology of the third millennium with the ability to cope with rapid changes in the world around (Jafari Moghaddam, 2006).

It is clear that with KM functions, especially knowledge distribution affect the innovation and financial success of organizations. Many studies have shown that the integration of intra and extra organizational knowledge improves innovation (Wong, 2005). Consequently, there is a direct relationship between the KM and the innovation creation such that the stronger the performance of KM, there is a positive effect on the increase of innovation (Moheb, 2016).

1.9 The relationship between innovation and organizational performance

Learning development in its various forms (individual, team, and organizational) is considered as an important factor in the economic success of organizations and is one of the important indicators of performance (Posch & Wiedenegger, 2014).

An organization that is prone to learning is likely to be able to innovate in products and processes by gaining the power of technology change, and the power of innovation will improve its performance. In other words, innovation is considered as an important force for company development and performance improvement. The power of innovation is the most important determinant of performance (Cooper, 2000). Innovative high-capacity firms can achieve competitive advantage and high performance through appropriate environmental adaptation and development of new capabilities. (Hult, Ferrell, 2007). Considering the assumptions of this research, the conceptual model of the research was considered in accordance with Fig. 1 as follows:

Figure 1: Conceptual model of research based on literatures

2. Research Method

The type of present research is operational in terms of its purpose (due to its ability to apply the results in service organizations and manufacturing companies, especially small and medium manufacturing enterprises) and the survey type in terms of collecting data (according to the distribution of the questionnaire) and field method (among the companies active in Eshtehard industrial township) and in terms of research method is descriptive and correlative. This case study was conducted among the managers of the active factories in Eshtehard Industrial Township. Accordingly, the statistical population was formed by managers of manufacturing factories of Alborz province in the Industrial Township of Eshtehard, with 600 active production units. In this research, the Cochran formula was used to determine the statistical sample size. Finally, 234 managers of production units located in Eshtehard Industrial Township were considered as the sample. In order to perform sampling, all 600 units were coded with numbers from 1 to 600 and then 234 random numbers were created between 1 and 600, and manufacturing units whose codes were equal to random numbers of production were selected. It should be noted that 240 questionnaires were distributed in this study. Finally, 236 healthy questionnaires were collected by taking into account the drop in the questionnaires.

A summary of the demographic characteristics of the statistical samples is as follows: Most of the audience group was male managers with frequency of 188 (80%). Also, the absolute and relative frequency of the status for age groups of respondents showed that the managers of the age group 41 to 50 years with the frequency of 121 cases (51%) were the most frequent observed samples of this study. Meanwhile, 89% of the samples had university education.

A questionnaire was used to collect data. For this purpose, theoretical and empirical research has been carried out. Using a previous study, a researcher-made questionnaire was used. The validity of this questionnaire was evaluated in the form of narrative and content based on the views of experts in this field and after some revision was approved. Finally, the validity of each constructs was measured by factor analysis and the results are presented in the findings section. Another validity based on convergent validity (AVE¹) was also tested. In the reliability section, the Cronbach's coefficient alpha was investigated, which can be seen in Table 1: In this study, the data are collected in both field and library formats and in two forms of information or secondary and primary data:

¹ Average Variance Extracted

Table 1: The results of Convergent Validity and Cronbach's Alpha for each of the variables

Variables	numbers	AVE	Cronbach's coefficient alpha
Knowledge-oriented culture	7	0.628	0.836
Knowledge-oriented leadership	5	0/745	0.812
Knowledge creation process	6	0/721	0.901
Organizational Performance	7	0/775	0/825
Innovation performance	9	0/635	0/792
KM practices	8	0/672	0/735

In this research, structural equation modeling was used to test the hypotheses. Due to the fact that the distribution of the data obtained in this study (according to the results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and the study of the standard amount of skewness and kurtosis of data) was reported abnormally, so in the structural analysis section, partial least square (SMART. PLS2) method was used.

3. Results

Table 2 shows the results of descriptive analysis for the variables of this research.

Table 2: Descriptive analysis of research variables (n = 236)

Variables	Mean	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Knowledge-oriented culture	2/5850	/71079	1/00	5/00
Knowledge-oriented leadership	3/0494	/66544	1/14	5/00
Knowledge creation process	2/6203	/75854	1/00	4/75
Organizational Performance	2/8842	/66933	1/00	4/80
Innovation performance	3/2907	/71234	1/00	4/67
KM practices	3/2511	/63037	1/00	5/00

The findings of this study confirm that in some variables, the value is higher than the cut-off point, and in some variables, the value is lower than that (considering the use of the Likert scale in this study, the numerical value of 3 as the criterion or average value is considered in the range of 1 to 5). The organizational performance of the manufacturing companies surveyed in this study was reported to be lower than the average (2.88), which indicates an unfavorable situation for them. In addition, the knowledge creation process has also shown a bad situation (2.62). The results of the correlation coefficient between the variables are reported in Table 3.

Table 3: The results of correlation coefficient (n = 236)

		1	2	3	4	5	6
1	Knowledge-oriented culture	1					
2	Knowledge-oriented leadership	0.650**	1				
3	Knowledge creation process	0.505**	0.545**	1			
4	Innovation performance	0.590**	0.693**	0.667**	1		
5	KM practices	0.155	0.438**	0.279**	0.303**	1	
6	Organizational Performance	0.296**	0.461**	0.461**	0.413**	0.657**	1

**Significance at the level of confidence is 99%.

Regarding the significance level of the test, it is determined that among the research variables there is a significant relationship at the 99% confidence level ($P < 0.01$). The results reported in Table 3 show that organizational performance has the highest correlation with the appropriate use of KM practices at 0.657.

In the following, structural equations modeling was used to answer the research hypotheses. Accordingly, in the beginning, the factor loadings were studied and then structural model research was investigated. Factor loadings are calculated by calculating the correlation of the indices of a structure with that structure, which, if this value is equal to or greater than 0.4, confirms that the variance between the structure and its indices is greater than variance of the measurement error of that structure and the reliability of this model is reasonable. In structural equation modeling, two

indicators of "significant t " and "R²" are investigated. If the value of the significance coefficients t is 1.96, 2.58, 3.27, it shows the correctness of the relationship between the structures and, as a result, the research hypotheses confirmed 95%, 99% and 99.9% at the confidence level respectively. The results of factor loadings and significant numbers are presented in Table 4:

Table 4: Factor loading and significant numbers for each research structure

Subscales	Factor loading value	Significant of loading factor coefficients
Knowledge-oriented culture	0.736 up to 0.806	12/847 up to 20/782
Knowledge-oriented leadership	0.859 up to 0.881	25/749 up to 33/868
Knowledge creation process	0.704 up to 0.870	13/142 up to 30/372
Innovation performance	0.691 up to 0.857	11/552 up to 26/836
KM practices	0.668 up to 0.793	9/712 up to 19/740
Organizational Performance	0.661 up to 0.830	5/541 up to 24/282

According to the results presented in Table 4, it can be stated that in all cases the coefficients of the factor loadings are greater than 0.4, and this indicates the fitting of the measuring models. Also, significant coefficients with a value above 1/96 confirmed the significance of factor loadings coefficients. The results of the confirmatory factor analysis show that all of the structures of this research have been fitted with appropriate measurement models. Accordingly, in the following, a structural model is presented in which the coefficients and the path coefficients are presented (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: The model of the research, with regression coefficients and t-value coefficients

As shown in Fig. 2, the regression coefficient has been reported to be higher than 0.4 in all of the existing paths, indicating the suitability of the variables' influence. However, in order to examine the significance of factor loading (β), a significant number (t) was investigated. If the value of significant numbers is less than 1/96, it indicates that the path is not approved, in other words, the hypothesis is rejected on this path. The results of the significant numbers model in Fig. 2 show the significance of regression coefficients. In addition to the path coefficients that yield important results, we can also refer to the determination coefficient, which is displayed through numerical values within the structures. According

to Figure 2, it can be stated that the set of effective factors on the manufacturing companies performance in this model, can explain 86.3% of the company's performance changes (R-Square = 0.863). In addition, the role of intermediary of the knowledge creation process in the relationship between knowledge culture and knowledge leadership with organizational performance is significant, so that, according to the Sobel test, the influence coefficient was 0.575 and 0.452 respectively ($P < 0.01$). In relation to the intermediary role of management practices (in influencing culture and knowledge leadership on innovation performance) this was 0.863 and 0.452, respectively.

4. Discussion

According to the findings of the present study, knowledge-oriented culture has an impact on knowledge-oriented leadership. According to Oliver & Kandadi (2009), the knowledge culture is a form of organizational life that enables individuals to create, share, and use knowledge to benefit from and sustain the organization's success. As the Akhavan and Imani (2015) have stated, the component of culture as the most influential and social factor and technology are considered as the most important factors in the sharing of knowledge. Prior to any activity in the process of KM, we must invest in the culture topic. In fact, culture is the backbone of KM, reducing costs in knowledge generation and improving organizational performance, creating a collaborative culture among employees creates group activities in their work. Cultural factors can be considered as failures of KM, which can be turned into success by solving problems. They consider knowledge-oriented culture to be a culture that values knowledge, and encourages creation, sharing and employing them. According to Asaghar (2013), the development of knowledge-oriented culture, along with the encouragement of behaviors such as the creation and sharing of knowledge, is one of the objectives of KM initiatives in the organization. Culture has a deep link with knowledge in organizations. In fact, any discussion of knowledge in the organization's environment without a specific reference to its cultural status is like moving in the wrong. The need to pay attention to organizational culture is to the extent that the experts believe that if there is an effective and sustainable change in an organization, its culture must be changed. In other words, the success and failure of organizations should be sought in its culture. Therefore, managers, relying on culture and exploiting it, can free themselves from traditional solutions and provide new solutions for the growth of the organization and its development. In general, consistent with the findings of the research, according to Oliver & Kandadi (2009), it can be stated that the influence of cultural factors on the effectiveness of KM programs is undeniable; the culture of each organization, due to the inclusion of a value system, affects the behavior of individuals. According to the findings of the present study, knowledge-oriented culture has an impact on the knowledge creation process. In explaining the concept of the knowledge creation process, one can say that the activities of the organization individuals begin to prove or justify their obligations and attitudes towards the assigned duties. In such a process, people can easily submit their mental assumptions. Assumptions, high-minded intuitions and beliefs are considered as the source of organizational knowledge creation. According to Davenport, and Prusak (2000), knowledge creation and sharing it are intangible activities that cannot be created by force. Only when knowledge-oriented culture is felt and created by the members of the organization can knowledge creation lead to excellence merit. Hence, cooperation, coordination and empowered teams of employees should be considered as standard attitudes in the KM environment and supported. Proper knowledge-oriented culture can have a positive tendency to share knowledge and innovation. This finding is consistent with the findings of the present study. In the present study, the results also show that knowledge-oriented culture affects the process of knowledge creation. Vazifeh Doost et al (2012) on the impact and importance of culture in knowledge creation and dissemination has argued that the knowledge creation culture leads to the creation of synergistic harmonization environments. If an organization values and culture, encourage learning and knowledge creation, all functions of the organization will change.

The results have shown that knowledge-oriented culture has an impact on KM practices. Mahjub (2011) based on his study about the effect of knowledge-oriented culture, states that knowledge, especially the implicit knowledge, will be disseminated if its appropriate culture is created. In order to create an appropriate culture for the transfer and exchange of knowledge, managers must move away from fear-oriented approaches so that individuals can easily express their knowledge even if such knowledge sharing does not produce significant and meaningful results. The realization of this approach requires the abandonment of obedience-based controls and the move towards commitment-based control approaches. According to Lange, P. and Coltham (2009), we can say that the importance of the knowledge-oriented culture in the organization for the success of knowledge creation is due to the fact that any organizational change will be successful when the whole organization and all its members are committed to this process of change and all try to succeed. Effective implementation of practices for the process of creating knowledge also requires the adoption and universal support, and there must be certain behaviors and attitudes among the members of the organization.

Research findings also showed that knowledge-oriented leadership has an impact on the knowledge creation process. In explaining this, one can refer to Sobhi's view (2011), which according to his study states that knowledge-oriented leadership should be considered as a model that has the ability to transform organizational transformations, as well as the ability to advance and develop positive thinking organizations in which individuals are in peace and the performance of the organization can not only be associated with this, but it can also be maximized. One of these functions is knowledge creation, which brings competitive advantage to organizations. In fact, the factors that can accelerate or threaten the

creation of knowledge in the organization is the role of leadership in the organization. As Adli (2006) believes, achieving knowledge creation is one of the requirements of any organization. Knowledge creation with the organization appropriate leadership style has a two-sided relationship. Knowledge-oriented leadership encourages individuals to create knowledge and always tries to induce the importance of knowledge creation within an organization's environment. On the other hand, research findings have also shown that knowledge-oriented leadership has an impact on KM practices. This important issue, has a common ground with previous assumptions. In this regard, Teece (2009) has argued that knowledge leaders must recognize such efforts by employees and reward them instead of encouraging negative behaviors that put the transfer, sharing and exploitation of knowledge at risk. In order to benefit from the processes of discovery and knowledge extraction, organizational leadership in knowledge-oriented organizations means leadership through knowledge. In other words, the leaders of the organization must lead the knowledge workers to learn and apply knowledge and thereby achieve the goals of the organization's knowledge. Knowledge-oriented leadership implies ownership of the key role of KM in the organization, which leads to the recognition, identification and exploitation of opportunities for innovation. On the other hand, according to Rosing (2011), to strengthen and promote innovation in the organization, leaders have to integrate divergent behaviors depending on the circumstances of the situation. Very creative and innovative organizations, combining exploration and knowledge extraction activities to achieve dual power, must be able to direct members of the organization to achieve goals in different circumstances, based on distinct requirements. Also, in explaining this finding, we can refer to the point of view of Schermerhorn (2012), which states that, generally, the combined model of knowledge leadership should lead the KM techniques to create, transfer, store and apply knowledge in the organization. In addition, knowledge-oriented leadership should include transparent communication, taking into account the expectations of knowledge workers and the goals of the organization, as well as motivational elements. First, leaders should act as advisors so that employees can figure out how their jobs and their actions lead to provide communication. In addition, communication is essential for leaders to demonstrate clearly the organization's expectations of employees regarding their work and the removal of communication barriers. This is in line with the findings of the present research, which demonstrates the important role of leadership in KM practices. The positive impact of knowledge creation on organizational performance is another finding of this study. This is one of the main assumptions of this research, which indicates whether the performance of manufacturing companies can be a function of their knowledge creation process, which according to the findings of this research, this issue is confirmed. In explaining these findings, Zarrin (2011) points out that according to the importance of organizations in the 21st century, the necessity of paying attention to KM is undeniable. Informative orientation of organizations to KM will provide their relief from traditional bureaucratic structures and turning to new management systems in the world. In this regard, Alegre et al. (2013) have stated that global competition and the challenges facing the business and industry have put pressure on organizations to create sustainable competitive advantage. Knowledge is considered as the basis and the main factor of competition. Alongside knowledge, innovation is also considered as the main driving force for the prosperity and success of organizations and the economy as a whole. On the other hand, for organizations, the customer is the focus of profitability and growth and should be the focus of attention. Since KM is considered as one of the infrastructure factors in creating technical and managerial systems, the use of KM along with customer relationship management provides organizations with the opportunity to more likely identify market opportunities the result of the above explains that the process of knowledge creation is one of the most important components for achieving organizational performance.

The impact of the knowledge creation process on innovation performance has been confirmed in the present study positively. As Dehghan Najm (2009) states, nowadays innovation in the present technological space is necessary for organizations, and most organizations are looking for new ideas. In this regard, the organization's experts are trying to use their knowledge to provide new products or services that customers need and create a foundation that innovation as learning can be a continuous process because the purpose of KM and the secret of survival of these modern organizations lies in innovation. Also, as stated by Baladehi and Arabi (2014), the conscious management wants to use more and more tools called knowledge to confront and deal with factors of uncertainty, maintaining position and creating creativity and innovation to expand the competitive arena. This requires the organization to prioritize KM as a strategic and necessary need and include it among its priority programs in order to advance in the field of competitiveness. In modern world, societies and organizations are seeking sustainable competitive advantage. Along with the findings of this research, Jafari Moghaddam (2006) suggested that KM is a useful tool for organizations to develop their capital, encourage innovation, and maximize desirable performance. Using effectively of existing knowledge, the readiness to receive and using new information and modern knowledge to develop knowledge and technology of the third millennium, will be possible with the ability to deal with the rapid changes in the world around us. Accordingly, the study of Jafari Moghaddam (2006) can be considered in line with the findings of the current research and stated that today the knowledge creation process has an undeniable role as one of the factors influencing innovation performance. The findings also confirmed that KM practices affect the performance of innovation. This is one of the main hypotheses of this research, which has a common ground with the previous hypothesis. What is understood from this hypothesis is that, in any case, the use of KM in modern manufacturing companies is one of the most important and effective factors on the innovation performance of companies, which can in turn affect organizational performance. The final hypothesis has been addressed. Howells (2008) explains the necessity of using KM practices in order to improve the performance of innovation. For many thinkers, development

and management of human intellectual skills is more important than the management and development of capital and physical resources. Although the aforementioned topic is conceptually simple and obvious, but as a practice, creating, maintaining, implementing, expanding and updating the organizational knowledge base in such a way that it can play the supportive role of organizational innovation as best possible way, is difficult for many organizations. KM will make the best use of the individual's creativity and expertise and, ultimately, increase the organization's competitive ability. In other words, the organization should, through the KM tools, direct implicit knowledge of individuals to innovation. In explaining the findings of the present research, whether KM practices are effective on the performance of corporate innovation, it can be argued that using the KM roles in the organization's innovation process, one can say that it facilitates the cooperation of the organization's functional boundaries, helping to create capabilities and also reduce complexity in the innovation process. Finally, the findings indicate that innovation performance affects organizational performance. In general, and in light of all the findings of the present research, it can be argued that the purpose of using KM practices is to create a better innovation performance (Zack et al., 2009; Darroch, McNaughton, 2002) and more desirable organizational performance (Pandey, Dutta, 2013; Nonaka, Toyama, 2003). This is consistent with the findings of the present research. In practice, it can be stated that in modern manufacturing companies, KM and Knowledge leadership are among the important factors in achieving innovation and consequently in achieving organizational performance. In addition, the findings of the present study are consistent with the results of Faraj Allahzadeh's (2013) on banks and the study of Sedaghat (2012) on Social Security Organization.

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